

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF PARENTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN'S PERSONALITY IN THE MODERN WORLD

Quliyeva S.

*PhD in psychology, associate professor,
Department of Psychology, Baku State University;
Baku, Azerbaijan;*

Nasirova N.

*PhD in psychology, Department of Psychology,
Baku State University
Baku, Azerbaijan*

Valiyeva V.

*PhD in psychology, Department of Psychology,
Baku State University
Baku, Azerbaijan*

Hajiyeva I.

*MS in psychology, Department of Psychology
Baku, Azerbaijan*

Abstract

The article presents an analysis of modern views of scientists on the problem of formation of relationships of a child with others, substantiates theoretical and empirical materials on the problem under study, as well as the influence of family relationships on the psycho-emotional state of a child. Based on the study of a large volume of literature, the degree of influence of the nature of family relationships on the psycho-emotional state of a child is revealed. The authors consider the emotional component of family relationships as a leading component in determining their constructiveness, describe family relationships that affect the level of anxiety and aggression of preschool children, diagnose the attitude of parents (primarily mothers) to different aspects of family life (family role), anxiety and aggression of a preschooler. Using various psychological techniques, the article examines parental attitudes and reactions, their anxiety and aggression that occur in family relationships, analyzes the relationship between the psycho-emotional state of a child and the nature of family relationships.

Keywords: family, parental interpersonal relationships, psycho-emotional state of child, well-being of children.

LITERATURE REVIEW: At present, the problem of family relations and the psycho-emotional state of the child are becoming especially relevant and have a huge impact on the formation of the child's relationships with others.

The following factors are distinguished that influence the socialization of a person: family, in any type of culture the family acts as the main unit in which the socialization of the individual takes place; "equality relations", inclusion in "groups of equals", i.e. friends of the same age; schooling, this is a formal process - a certain range of subjects. There is also a "hidden" curriculum: the rules of school life, the authority of the teacher, the teacher's reaction to the actions of children, equality relations, etc.; mass media, this is a very strong factor in influencing the behavior and views of people; work, in all types of culture work is an important factor in the socialization of the individual; organizations, youth associations, churches, free associations, sports clubs also play their role in socialization

Family has a decisive influence on the mental development of children (Bell, 1979; Brim, 1957). When a child is born, we want him to be healthy and develop well mentally. And only later, we think about what kind of person he will become. Over time, the child masters the general forms of behavior inherent to a person

among people and develops as an individual. By accepting a positive relationship with his parents and loved ones, the child will develop well (Bell, 1979). After all, a good attitude from parents is vital for a child and if he is brought up in a family where love and affection reign, this has a positive effect on his development. As psychological and pedagogical studies show, a special influence on a small child is exerted by the family circle of communication, which includes parents, brothers, sisters and other close people who satisfy the child's need to be protected, loved. And if a child is brought up in a family where he is understood and supported, then he is especially sensitive to their educational influences.

Family is a microcosm of culture, a culture of everyday life, poorly structured from the point of view of a rational approach to socialization. Family socialization should be attributed to spontaneous socialization, which is based both on the conscious actions of family members and on the unconscious, while both are constantly changing, their share in the overall process is subject to dynamics. The function of the unconscious is to resist consciousness, and the function of co-consciousness in relation to the unconscious is control (Yudina, 2014).

In a normal, prosperous family, a child is surrounded by the care and attention of adults, and, it

would seem, there should be no reason to worry. However, even among such children, there is a very high risk of mental illness, including neuroses. Therefore, parents from the first days of a child's life need to take into account the possibility of deviations in the neuropsychic development of children and know the reasons for such deviations. Parents should remember that neuroses do not occur in children if parents deal with their personal problems in a timely manner, do not quarrel in the presence of their children, do not sort things out in front of them, but on the contrary, maintain warm relationships, love their relatives and children. Parents should be friendly to them, responsive to their needs and requests, simple and direct in communication, give children the opportunity to express their feelings and

stabilize the emerging problems in a timely manner (Mowder, 2005).

Ginsburg and colleagues searched family relations and its impact on children. The authors mentioned that with added anxiety over their inability to adequately predict the future, they become susceptible to the promises of success and full preparation offered by all of the special enrichment programs and vulnerable to the belief that if their children are at least exposed to everything, they will have the best chance to be prepared (Ginsburg et al., 2007).

There can be observed various problems in parent-child relationship. These problems were mentioned in the following picture:

Picture 1. Parent children relationship problems

When unresolved experiences arise for a child, it is necessary to note a chronic psychotraumatic situation as a source of persistent mental stress. Against this background, mental traumas and emotional shocks additionally act, increasing the pathogenicity of a life situation, since the child cannot cope with them and survive them. Together with an internal conflict, problems in communication and unfavorable life circumstances, this indicates the emergence of an unsuccessful, traumatic life experience, and can lead to a state of chronic distress, as the main source of painful tension in neuroses. All this is complicated by the fact that children with neuroses cannot, due to their limited and already psychogenically deformed life experience, upbringing conditions and relationships in the family, emotionally react to the accumulating neuropsychic stress. Children are forced to suppress it, which exceeds the limit of adaptive capabilities and changes the neuropsychic reactivity of the body. And if stress that has been acting for a long time exceeds the adaptive capabilities of children, does not allow them to express themselves, to assert themselves in vital positions, to resolve a traumatic situation in time, then it undermines the ability to ade-

quately perceive themselves, accompanied by a decrease in self-esteem, lack of self-confidence, in their strengths and capabilities, fears and anxiety, a feeling of helplessness. Therefore, ideas of self-destruction, inferiority, damage, inability to be themselves among other peers develop (Cox et al., 2003).

Children growing up in an atmosphere of love and understanding have fewer health problems, difficulties with learning, communication with peers, and vice versa, disruption of parent-child relationships can lead to the formation of various psychological problems and complexes. From psychological and pedagogical literature, we see that the main conditions for success in raising children in a family can be considered a normal family atmosphere, which is characterized as:

- awareness by parents of their duty and sense of responsibility for raising children, consisting of mutual respect between father and mother, constant attention to the educational, work and social life of their child, help and support him in difficult situations, and careful attitude to the dignity of each family member;

- organization of life and everyday life of the family, which is based on the equality of all members, involvement of children in solving economic issues of family life, housekeeping, involvement in work;

- in the organization of family leisure, i.e. participation in sports and hiking trips, joint walks, listening to music, reading books, visiting the theater and cinema;

- mutual fundamental exactingness, goodwill in treatment, sincerity, love and cheerfulness in the family. Thus, family relationships are the source of mental illness that affects the development of the child.

Therefore, parents should understand that the family atmosphere is a decisive factor in the formation of the child's personality, and also that the further development of the child, the attitude towards himself, his family and the people around him largely depends on the attitude of the parents and other family members towards the child, on the satisfaction of his mental needs (Ling et.al.2005).

Parents, of course, can and should make demands on their child, based on the goals of education, moral standards, specific situations in which it is necessary to make pedagogically and morally justified decisions. However, those of them who prefer orders and violence to all types of influence, encounter resistance from the child, who responds to pressure, coercion, threats with his own countermeasures: hypocrisy, deception, outbursts of rudeness, and sometimes outright hatred. But even if the resistance is broken, many valuable personal qualities are broken along with it: independence, self-esteem, initiative, faith in oneself and one's abilities.

Blind authoritarianism of parents, ignoring the interests and opinions of the child, systematically depriving him of the right to vote in deciding issues related to him - all this guarantees serious failures in the formation of his personality. Guardianship in the family is a system of relations in which parents, by ensuring the satisfaction of all the child's needs with their work, protect him from any worries, efforts and difficulties, taking them upon themselves. The issue of active personality development fades into the background. Another

problem is at the center of educational influences - satisfying the child's needs and protecting him from difficulties.

Parents, in fact, block the process of serious preparation of their children for a collision with reality beyond the threshold of their home. It is these children who are less adapted to life in a group. According to psychological observations, it is this category of teenagers that gives the greatest number of breakdowns in transitional age. It is precisely these children, who, it would seem, have nothing to complain about, begin to rebel against excessive parental guardianship. If dictatorship presupposes violence, orders, harsh authoritarianism, then guardianship - care, protection from difficulties. However, the results are largely the same: children lack independence, initiative, they are one way or another removed from solving issues that concern them personally, and even more so from general family problems (Nomaguchi, 2016).

The system of interpersonal relationships in the family, based on the recognition of the possibility and even the expediency of independent existence of adults from children, can be generated by the tactics of "non-interference". It is assumed that two worlds can coexist: adults and children, and neither should cross the line thus outlined. Most often, this type of relationship is based on the passivity of parents as educators. Cooperation as a type of relationship in the family presupposes the mediation of interpersonal relationships in the family by common goals and objectives of joint activities, their organization and high moral values. It is in this situation that the egoistic individualism of the child is overcome. A family, where the leading type of relationship is cooperation, acquires a special quality, becomes a group of a high level of development - a team (Price et.al., 2005).

Parents and children communication need to be effective, in this case they can develop a lot of skills, not only academically, and also social-emotional skills, and abilities. These skills were described in the following picture:

Picture 2. *Effective communication in the family*

Adequate and inadequate behavior of a child depends on the conditions of upbringing in the family. Children with low self-esteem are dissatisfied with themselves. This happens in a family where parents constantly reproach the child or set high goals for him. The child feels that he does not meet the requirements of the parents. (Do not tell the child that he is ugly, this creates complexes that are impossible to get rid of later.) Inadequacy can also manifest itself with inflated self-esteem. This happens in a family where the child is often praised, and gifts are given for little things and achievements (the child gets used to material rewards). The child is punished very rarely, the system of demands is very soft (Mowder, 2005).

Adequate representation - here a flexible system of punishment and praise is needed. Admiration and praise are excluded in his presence. Gifts are rarely given for actions. Extremely harsh punishments are not used. In families where children with high, but not inflated, self-esteem grow up, attention to the child's personality (his interests, tastes, relationships with friends) is combined with sufficient demands. Here, humiliating punishments are not used and the child is readily praised when it deserves it. Children with low self-esteem (not necessarily very low) enjoy greater freedom at home, but this freedom is, in essence, a lack of control, a consequence of parents' indifference to their children and to each other. School performance is an important criterion for assessing a child as a person by adults and peers. The attitude towards oneself as a student is largely determined by family values. The child's qualities that most concern his parents come to the fore - maintaining prestige (at home, questions are asked: "Who else got an A?"), obedience ("Did you get scolded today?"), etc. In the self-awareness of a young schoolchild, the emphasis shifts when parents are concerned not with academic, but with everyday aspects of his school life ("Is there a draft from the windows in the classroom?", "What did they give you for breakfast?"),

or are generally not concerned with anything - school life is not discussed or is discussed formally. A rather indifferent question: "What happened at school today?" will sooner or later lead to the corresponding answer: "Nothing special", "Everything is fine". Parents also set the initial level of the child's aspirations - what he claims in educational activities and relationships. Children with a high level of aspirations, inflated self-esteem and prestigious motivation count only on success. Their ideas about the future are just as optimistic. Children with a low level of aspirations and low self-esteem do not claim much either in the future or in the present. They do not set high goals for themselves and constantly doubt their capabilities, quickly resigning themselves to the level of academic performance that develops at the beginning of their studies. Anxiety can become a personality trait at this age. High anxiety becomes stable with constant dissatisfaction with learning on the part of parents. Let's say a child is sick, has fallen behind his classmates and finds it difficult to join the learning process. If the temporary difficulties he is experiencing irritate adults, anxiety and fear of doing something badly, incorrectly arise. The same result is achieved in a situation where the child is studying quite successfully, but parents expect more and make inflated, unrealistic demands (Thompson, 2008).

Due to the increase in anxiety and the associated low self-esteem, academic achievements decrease, failure is consolidated. Lack of self-confidence leads to a number of other characteristics - the desire to mindlessly follow the instructions of an adult, to act only according to models and templates, fear of taking the initiative, formal assimilation of knowledge and methods of action. Adults, dissatisfied with the child's declining productivity in school work, increasingly focus on these issues in their communication with him, which increases emotional discomfort. It turns out to be a vicious circle: the child's unfavorable personal character-

istics are reflected in his educational activity, such performance causes a corresponding reaction from others, and this negative reaction, in turn, intensifies the child's characteristics. This circle can be broken by changing the parents' attitudes and assessments. Close adults, concentrating on the child's slightest achievements. Without reproaching him for individual shortcomings, reduce his anxiety level and thus contribute to the successful completion of educational tasks (Baydar, 2003).

The second option is demonstrativeness - a personality trait associated with an increased need for success and attention from others. The source of demonstrativeness is usually a lack of attention from adults to children who feel abandoned and "underloved" in the family. But it happens that a child is given sufficient attention, but it does not satisfy him due to a hypertrophied need for emotional contacts. Excessive demands on adults are made not by neglected children, but, on the contrary, by the most spoiled children. Such a child will seek attention, even breaking the rules of behavior. ("Better to be scolded than not noticed"). The task of adults is to do without lectures and admonitions, to make comments as less emotionally as possible, not paying attention to minor offenses and punishing for major ones (say, by refusing a planned trip to the circus). This is much more difficult for an adult than a careful attitude towards an anxious child. If for a child with high anxiety the main problem is constant disapproval of adults, then for a demonstrative child it is a lack of praise (Yudina, 2014).

The third option is escape from reality. It is observed in cases where children combine demonstrativeness with anxiety. These children also have a strong need for attention to themselves, but they cannot realize it due to their anxiety. They are hardly noticeable, are afraid of causing disapproval with their behavior, strive to fulfill the requirements of adults. An unmet need for attention leads to an increase in even greater passivity, invisibility, which complicates already insufficient contacts. When adults encourage children's activity, show attention to the results of their studies and the search for creative self-realization, a relatively easy correction of their development is achieved (Yudina, 2014).

To sum up these materials, it can be mentioned that parents need to believe in the uniqueness of their child, they need to accept them as they are, relying on their strengths. Do not be shy to show them your love, you need to make it clear that they will always be loved, under any circumstances. As an influence, it is necessary to use rewards more often than punishments. At the same time, they should try to ensure that parental love does not turn into permissiveness and neglect. They should strictly adhere to the prohibitions and permissions set, do not rush to resort to punishment, parent need to try to influence the child with requests. They need to help the child learn to express his feelings, analyze the actions and behavior of other people, drawing certain conclusions from this.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION:

Parents play the most important role in the overall development of their child. It is the right guidance of parents that develops the character of the child. The role of

parents in child development is responsive. These responsibility is never-ending. According to literature materials the family has special impact in the following areas.

- Cognitive development;
- Socio-cultural development;
- Physical development;
- Mental development;
- Spiritual development.

To sum up all the ideas some of the effective tips can be helpful for both of the parents and children: being positive, being sensitive for child's need, being emotionally present, and communicating effectively, respecting child's feeling and others.

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